

ISSN : 2349-543X

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF

TRENDS IN COMMERCE AND ECONOMICS

Indexed by:

Universal
Impact Factor

IMPACT FACTOR
SEARCH

Editorial board

Professor Ruthes Aguilera USA Northeastern University- USA

Professor Herman Aguinis

George Washington University School of Business- USA

Professor Pat Auger

Melbourne Business School- Australia

Professor Pratima Bansal

Ivey Business School, Western University- Canada

Professor Michael Barnett

Rutgers University Newark Business School- USA

Russell W. Belk

Schulich School of Business, York University, Canada

10/25 Thamocharan Street, Arisipalayam, Salem, India

Principal Contact

Academic Journal Online

info@academicjournalonline.org

THEORETICAL BASIS OF OPTIMAL TAXATION OF PROFITS

Makhmudov Ilkhom Egamovich

Chief specialist of the monitoring department of the Surkhondare regional branch of
the mortgage bank ATIB.

ilhomm013@gmail.com

Abstract. This article argues that, according to the experience of developed countries in the world, improving the corporate tax system is of great importance in ensuring economic stability, increasing business and investment activity. This requires the coordination of taxation and tax regulation in optimizing the taxation of profits of business entities.

Keywords: Profit, tax, corporate tax, import, tax incentives, business entities, marginal tax.

Enter

The structure of an optimal tax system has long been a topic of interest to both theoretical and practical economists. Eight general conclusions can be drawn from the development of optimal tax theory in recent decades:

- 1) the optimal marginal tax rate schedule depends on the distribution of ability;
- 2) the optimal marginal tax regime can decline at high incomes;
- 3) a flat tax with universal lump-sum transfers can be close to the optimal tax;
- 4) the optimal level of redistribution increases as income inequality increases;
- 5) taxes should be linked to personal qualities and income;
- 6) only final products should be taxed, and in general, they should be taxed uniformly;
- 7) income from capital should be exempt from tax at least initially;

The standard theory of optimal taxation states that the tax system should be chosen to maximize the social welfare function, subject to a number of constraints.¹

Main article

According to standard optimal taxation theory, intermediate goods and services are not taxed because the inefficiencies associated with production processes may be more costly than taxing final outputs. The optimal tax literature is usually viewed as an aid to the social planner, i.e. the social welfare function is based on the utility of individuals in society.

Although the development of modern optimal taxation theory in the early 1970s opened up a fruitful new field of research, it also created a major gap in the relationship between public finance theorists and practitioners. For many practicing economists working in governments and international organizations, the new theories of optimal taxation seemed too technical and abstract and were therefore not of great importance.

Even today, most practicing economists believe that optimal taxation theory has produced too few reliable results to be the basis for useful specific recommendations. Optimal taxation theory is normative, essentially assuming that policies are made by politicians who are sympathetic to individual preferences, as well as some social preferences for equality.

This theory can be refuted by noting that in reality politicians usually represent certain interest groups and that current policies reflect some compromise between conflicting interests rather than maximizing the Bergson–Samuelson social welfare function. We argue that optimal tax theory can actually be a very important resource for politicians in designing effective tax policies, and that recent theoretical research in this area can help to bridge the gap between scientific research and practical policy recommendations.

In general, the scientific research conducted by Ramsey, Diamond, and Mirrlees on the theory of optimal corporate taxation is considered the foundation of

¹Mankiw, N. Gregory, Matthew Charles Weinzierl, and Danny Ferris Yagan. 2009. Optimal taxation in theory and practice. *Journal of Economic Perspectives* 23(4). <https://dash.harvard.edu/bitstream/handle>.

the scientific literature on optimal taxation. Ramsey viewed consumption and savings as two different goods and argued that capital gains should be taxed at a much lower rate than income taxes on wages².

Diamond and Mirrlees argue that theories of optimal production in a planned economy typically assume that the tax system allows the government to achieve the desired redistribution of wealth. On the other hand, recent scholarly discussions on the criteria for public investment have largely ignored taxation as an additional method of controlling the economy.

Although the lump-sum transfers required for full optimality are not currently feasible, taxes on goods and income can be used to increase welfare. For this reason, taxes and social production are considered as control variables in maximizing social welfare³.

In studying this issue, Mantell used an analytical model to confirm his conclusions about the algebraic sign of the effect of a change in the income tax rate on the output of a firm facing an uncertain demand curve. Consider a firm operating in a market with significant market power. It faces the following demand function⁴:

$$P = D(Q, x) \quad (1.1)$$

where Q is the quantity of firm Q 's product offered for sale, P - is the unit price, $\frac{\partial}{\partial Q} D(Q, x) < 0$ and x is a randomly distributed variable. x The random variable is assumed to be defined by a probability distribution of the sum of the: $F(x^*) = Prob(x \leq x^*)$. x expected value \bar{x} is represented by.

CONCLUSION:

1. According to standard optimal taxation theory, intermediate goods and services are not taxed because the inefficiencies associated with production processes are likely to be more costly than taxing final outputs. Optimal profit tax theory The

²Ramsey, F.P. (1927). «A contribution to the theory of Taxation», E Economic Journal, vol. 37(145), pp.47-61. <https://eml.berkeley.edu/~saez/course131/Ramsey27.pdf>.

³Diamond P.A., Mirrlees J.A., 1971. Optimal Taxation and Public Production I: Production Efficiency. American Economic Review Vol. 61, No. 1, pp. 8-27. <http://hassler-j.iies.su.se/Courses/DynPubFin>.

⁴Mantell, E. H. 2019. A Theory of the Effect of Corporate Income Tax on the Optimal Output of a Firm Facing an Uncertain Demand. Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal, 6(4) 183. <https://journals.scholarpublishing.org/index.php/ASSRJ/article/view/6479/3865>.

research conducted by Ramsey, Diamond, and Mirrlees is considered the foundation of the scientific literature on optimal taxation.

2. Optimal production theories assume that a tax system can provide the government with the ability to effectively redistribute income. In any economic system where equality is valued, it can be assumed that progressive income taxes will become an important instrument of fiscal policy. Redistributive progressive taxation is usually related to the income of the taxpayer.

3. The application of corporate income tax at different rates in different sectors of the economy can lead to different equilibrium prices in the sectors, as well as to an increase in the remuneration of capital (for example, an increase in interest rates on loans in the financial sector). The tax burden in the sectors of the economy depends on the ratio of production factors of capital and labor and the elasticity of exchange between them.

LIST OF REFERENCES USED:

1. Abdullayev, D., 2023. O‘zbekistonda foyda solig‘i mamuriyatchiligini takomillashtirish. Iqtisodiy taraqqiyot va tahlil, 1(6), 108-115.

2. Adegbite, Tajudeen Adejare, Shittu Saheed Akande, 2017. The analysis of the impact of corporate income tax on investment in Nigeria. World Wide Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development <http://eprints.abuad.edu.ng/766/1/1507800932.pdf>.

3. Admati, A., P. DeMarzo, M. Hellwig and P. Pfleiderer. 2013. Fallacies, Irrelevant Facts, and Myths in the Discussion of Capital Regulation: Why Bank Equity is Not Socially Expensive. Working paper, Stanford University. https://homepage.coll.mpg.de/pdf_dat/2013_23online.pdf.

4. Aghion, P. and P. Howitt, 2008. The economics of growth. Cambridge and MA: MIT Press.

5. Aghion, P., U. Akcigit, and J. Fernandez-Villaverde, 2013. Optimal Capital Versus Labor Taxation with Innovation-Led Growth. PIER Working Paper Archive

International journal of trends in commerce and economics **ISSN:** 2349-543X VOL. 14. Issue 1

<http://academicjournalonline.org/index.php/ijtce/issue/archive>

[Impact factor 9](#)

13-025, Penn Institute for Economic Research, Department of Economics, University of Pennsylvania.